

31st International Symposium on Lepton Photon Interactions at High Energies

Title here

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On behalf of the ABC collaboration

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Abstract

Please provide proceedings for the Lepton Photon conference. The proceedings should be of a maximal length of 6 pages for an oral presentation and 4 pages for a poster. The deadline for uploading your proceedings is September 15, 2023 at 23:59 Australian Eastern Standard Time. Following this there will be a short review and you will be provided two weeks to update your proceedings. There will be no extensions.

Add your text here.